

Effectiveness versus legality of anti-smog drones

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Abstract:

Choking air, acrid, irritating throat and lungs smoke are the bane of the winter season and at the same time the cause of shortness of breath, dizziness, coughing, watery eyes and difficulty breathing. Air pollution is strongly related to smog. What legal actions should we take to minimize the problem?

Random and most often blind inspections are an insufficient form of anti-smog measures. No man is able to determine whether a given furnace and its chimney are a source of pollution without appropriate measuring devices. Besides, man, when moving in an urban area, only has a view of the situation from the face of the earth. Although the determination of a city official or guardian may be high, depending on individual physical conditions, he or she can patrol a specific area of the area. This translates directly into the efficiency and effectiveness of the activities carried out.

Drones appear where fast, accurate and large-scale intervention is necessary. Unmanned machines equipped with highly specialized sets of sensors will perform air quality monitoring works, check what comes out of the chimney and, most importantly, in what concentration. Anti-smog drones are a tool supporting local governments in the fight against air pollution. They make the inhabitants aware of the inevitable control at any moment of the day and night.

Key words: UAV, smog, sensors, pollution, environment

1. Introduction

Drones to fight smog are becoming more and more popular. The first tests of measuring air pollution from chimneys using drones are already underway. Currently, this technology is gaining even more popularity. This is favored by low temperatures, during which many residents start to burn in stoves to heat their homes. This situation - although it is definitely harmful to health - spurs further business. There are drone pollution measurement services on the market by licensed operators, but there are also companies that offer the purchase of the machines themselves. Offers are most often addressed to city offices, which - with the help of trained city guards - could constantly monitor the composition of the smoke coming out of the chimneys[3].

Hardly anyone will dare to say a bad word about the actions taken. After all, everything serves to improve the condition of our environment and fines those who burn garbage in their furnaces, thereby causing the emission of poisonous substances. Therefore, drones with measuring devices hanging above the chimneys of selected houses are perceived positively, and other cities and local anti-smog organizations compete in informing the media about taking further actions with the use of unmanned aerial vehicles. In this paper we will analyse the aviation law in the context of heavy drones hanging directly above the roofs of private houses. Are such flights fully legal?

The operator of the "anti-smog" drone must definitely have a UAV qualification certificate. It performs flights with a machine that weighs several kilograms with measuring equipment, and the flight itself cannot be included in either a "recreational" or "sports" flight.

The provisions of the regulation clearly indicate that the operator operating any drone must fly in such a way as not to disturb the peace or public order - what's more, fly so as not to expose anyone to harm. Does the flight of a heavy machine with apparatus over a private property meet these conditions? Does the noble purpose of the measurements allow an exception to be made?

There is no legal definition of "safe horizontal distance", but it is logical that some distance (other than "zero meters") must be provided horizontally so that the drone hanging above the building could avoid falling onto the building below it in the event of a failure. It is hard to imagine how the UAV hanging a meter from the chimney would maintain such a "safe distance" in accordance with the law.

In addition, the operator of an "anti-smog" drone cannot look into every chimney without the permission of the manager of the building over which he is flying.

2. Legal basis for conducting inspection activities

The control of compliance and application of the Environmental Protection Law is carried out by specific authorities. Under Art. 379 para. 1 of Environmental Protection Law of 21 April 2001 (Journal of Laws of 2021, item 1973) [8] the marshal of voivodship, starost and *wójt*, mayor or city president exercise control over the compliance and application of the Environmental Protection Law within the scope of competence of these authorities. These authorities may authorise employees of subordinate marshals' offices, district (*powiat*) offices, city or municipal (*gmina*) offices or municipal guard officers to perform inspection functions. According to Art. 379 para. 3(1) of the Environmental Protection Law, the inspector, while performing inspection, is entitled, inter alia, to enter the premises of the property, facility or its parts where business activity is conducted, together with experts and the necessary equipment 24 hours a day and between 6 a.m. and 10 p.m. – to the remaining area. The legal basis for the anti-smog operations is set out in Art. 379 of Environmental Protection Law. The inspector not only has the proper authority but also is entitled to enter the premises of the property with the necessary equipment, conduct tests or perform other inspection activities.

Taking the above into account, a drone operator may control the level of pollution emitted from the chimneys of a household provided that they have an appropriate authorisation to carry out control activities issued by the marshal of the voivodship, starost or *wójt*, mayor or city president.

In case of detecting the burning of improper fuel, the anti-smog patrol notifies officers or officials. They enter a selected house verifying the drone's indication, and in case of justified doubts, they additionally take samples from the furnace, checking the age and class of the heating device (boiler, furnace) against the requirements of the anti-smog resolution. Next, the samples are sent to a certified laboratory, with which the given office/municipal guard has an appropriate agreement. The laboratory carries out a physicochemical analysis following the methodology for detecting illegal waste incineration or co-incineration and then determines whether waste has been incinerated.

It is also worth remembering the Regional Air Improvement Program – Short Term Action Plan. There is a legal obligation to undertake a specified number of inspections during announced smog alert, i.e. exceeding the adopted standards of concentration of PM10, PM2.5 in the area of the given municipality (*gmina*) or voivodship. The anti-smog drone allows to concentrate on those chimneys which caused this phenomenon. However, part of the inspections is conducted by the city or municipal guard to fulfil the quantitative requirement – the required number of inspections and not the qualitative aspect – in this case identifying, reaching, revealing the polluter, and thus responsible for the smog formation. The effectiveness of anti-smog drone operations was confirmed by the test results. In the year 2021, in Kielce, more than 1,000 inspections of properties for burning prohibited materials were carried out, including almost 500 using a drone. Over 100 fines were imposed, 32 of which were based on drone smoke composition tests. Court motions were also prepared.

3. Drone operator's liability or the designation of the observer

The operator of an unmanned aerial vehicle with a take-off weight of 150 kg or less used solely in visual line of sight VLOS operation for purposes other than recreation or sport is not only a person with a certificate of competency.

The performance of flights to measure air quality entails the operator's liability. A person holding a UAV qualification certificate, i.e., the operator, is responsible for damages caused by the flight. It is worth noting that the purpose of the flight requires the presence of an observer during the flight. This is a person designated by the operator, who through visual observation of the flying model with the unaided eye, helps the operator to determine its position in the airspace and to ensure a safe distance from the other aircraft, obstacles, people, animals or property.

It is worth to establish the legal grounds for the liability of the drone operator and its eventual limitation in case of participation of an observer. The drone operator's liability is set out in the ordinance of the Minister of Infrastructure and Construction of 8 August 2016 amending the ordinance on the exclusion of the application of certain provisions of the Aviation Law to certain types of aircraft and defining the conditions and requirements for the use of such aircraft (Journal of Laws 2016, item 1317 as amended) **Błąd! Nie można odnaleźć źródła odwołania..**

When determining the responsibilities of a drone operator, there are two things to consider. Firstly, VLOS visual range operations for purposes other than recreation or sport. The purpose of using the drone is measurements of air pollutants from chimneys in the cities. Therefore, Annex 2 of the ordinance of the Minister of Infrastructure and Construction of 8 August 2016 amending the ordinance on the exclusion of the application of certain provisions of the Aviation Law to certain types of aircraft and defining the conditions and requirements for the use of such aircraft shall apply what has key importance in establishing i.e. maintaining distance. The performance of such a flight may involve damages, so it is critical to determine the basis and extent of liability.

Secondly, it is necessary to establish whether, in case of damage, the commission or executing entity is liable. Because we have a situation where there is an entity enforcing anti-smog regulations using various means, including a drone or obtaining evidence in the form of violations of anti-smog regulations, using drones.

3.1 The duty of particular care versus the liability of drone operator

The drone operator is required to exercise extreme caution. In this regard, the requirement also applies to flights performed to measure air quality. The duty of due care consists in increasing attention, adjusting the operator's behaviour or securing and adapting the place of take-off and landing of the unmanned aircraft or the area over which the flight is performed to conditions and situations changing during the flight, to the extent enabling the safe execution of the flight. When performing a flight, an operator shall exercise extreme caution and avoid any action or omission that could: a) endanger safety, including aviation safety; b) obstruct air traffic; c) disturb public peace or order, and d) expose anyone to harm.

The regulations of the ordinance on the exclusion of the application of certain provisions of the Aviation Law to certain types of aircraft and the defining the conditions and requirements for the use of such aircraft clearly indicate that the drone operator should perform flight in such a way as not to disturb the peace or public order, i.e. not to cause damage. Despite that the provisions of the ordinance define the duty of particular care as a full liability, in the event of its non-compliance, it shall burden the drone operator. The obligations and liability of the drone operator are also established in the ordinance.

The paramount obligation of the drone operator is the duty of particular care. However, in addition to this duty, they have to avoid any act or omission likely to cause a hazard to safety, including aviation safety, obstruction of air traffic, disturbance of the peace or public order, or damage to anyone.

The operator has to steer the unmanned aerial vehicle in such a manner as to avoid collision with other aircraft. They must ensure that the unmanned aerial vehicle, they are flying, gives priority of way to manned aircraft[6].

Another duty relates to the use of unmanned aircraft and controls. Their use should follow the recommendations and limitations specified by the manufacturer if published. Before each flight, they shall inspect the technical condition of the unmanned aircraft. Flights shall be conducted with an unmanned aircraft that is technically sound.

3.2 Safe distance

When a drone is used to make air quality measurements, it is evident that its flight is made over buildings. The drone operator is obligated to maintain a safe distance in case of failure or the loss of control over the unmanned aerial vehicle. However, it is worth noting - in the ordinance on the exclusion of the application of certain provisions of the Aviation Law to certain types of aircraft and the defining the conditions and requirements for the use of such aircraft – there is no definition of safe distance. The regulations that should be applied in that situation relate to the principles of flight operations by unmanned aircraft performed only within the visual range of the VLOS while maintaining the following conditions: ensuring in each phase of the flight a safe horizontal distance from persons, property, vehicles, structures or other airspace users, not at the disposal or control of the operator in case of failure or loss of control over the unmanned aircraft. However, the indication of the flight distance applies only to flights for recreational purposes. Flying models shall be operated at a horizontal distance of not less than 100 m from built-up areas of towns, cities, settlements or gatherings of people in the open air, and a horizontal distance of not less than 30 m from people, vehicles, structures that are not at the disposal or control of the operator[2].

However, the above regulation does not apply to the flights for purposes other than recreation, namely the flights which monitor compliance with environmental regulations. In case of smoke control from chimneys, the anti-smog drone is an unmanned aerial vehicle with a take-off

weight of 150 kg or less used solely in visual line of sight VLOS operation for purposes other than recreation or sport.

3.3 Drone operator liability

While establishing the scope of personal responsibility in flight operations, the regulation are of critical importance. Thereunder, the drone operator is liable for their decision to perform the flight and its correctness, and the designation and participation of the observer in-flight performance do not absolve them from the responsibility for the safety of air operations. Thus, said regulation unambiguously confirms the full liability of the drone operator. Irrelevant of whether the flight was performed with an observer.

As follows from Art. 206 of the Aviation Law, liability for damage caused by the aircraft operation is subject to civil law provisions on liability for damage caused by mechanical means of communication moved by natural forces. The drone operator's liability is defined in Art 435 and 436 of the Civil Code and it is strict liability.

Considering the above, it is worth emphasizing that the drone operator is liable for the decision to perform the flight and its correctness and that the designation and participation of the observer in-flight performance do not absolve them from the responsibility for the safety of air operations.

4. Safety aspects in the regulatory framework

The Convention on International Civil Aviation (hereinafter the "Chicago Convention"), although signed in 1944, so long before the UAV became popular, contained a provision relating to the principles of their use. We are talking about her art. 8 with the following wording: "An aircraft capable of flying without a pilot may fly without a pilot over the territory of a Contracting State only with the special authorization of that State and in accordance with the terms of such authorization. Each contracting State undertakes to ensure control of the flights of aircraft without a pilot in areas open to civil aircraft in such a way as to avoid danger to civil aircraft. " It is worth noting here that pursuant to Art. 8 unmanned ships are treated similarly to those with crew, insofar as in the case of each of them, a flight over the territory of a foreign country may take place only with its prior consent.

The provisions of the quoted Chicago Convention[9] are subject to successive changes, which is directly related to the progressive development of aviation and the newly emerging technical and operational issues. As regards UAVs themselves, following A. Konert and P. Kasprzyk [10], mention should be made of the changes to Annex 2 to the Chicago Convention, introducing to the definition of UAV a general requirement that UAV operations should be carried out in such a way as to minimize the risk to people, property and other aircraft, as well as the specification of the requirements for issuing the authorization to perform a UAV crossing the state border.

The Annex also distinguishes the functions related to the operation of the UAV into the following: remotely operated aircraft system operator, remotely operated aircraft pilot and remotely operated aircraft observer. Thus, an UAV operator is a person, organization or enterprise engaged in or intending to operate / use a remote-control aircraft system, and a remote pilot is an authorized person. by the user to perform the duties essential to the operation of a remotely operated aircraft that properly controls the aircraft during its flight. Finally, the UAV observer is a trained competent person, designated by the operator, who, by visual observation of the remotely piloted aircraft, assists the pilot in the safe conduct of the flight. The said Appendix 4 to the Annex defines "Remotely piloted aircraft systems." It also confirms that an unmanned aerial vehicle is an aircraft and that, in principle, the provisions relating to manned ships (registration, unlawful taking, marking used, etc.) apply to it.

Art. 12 of the Chicago Convention, which reads as follows: "Each Contracting State undertakes to take appropriate measures to ensure that any aircraft that flies over its territory or maneuvers within its territory, as well as any aircraft bearing its national emblem, regardless of place of in which it is located must comply with local rules and regulations relating to the flight and maneuvering of aircraft. Each contracting State undertakes to keep its own regulations in this field, to the greatest extent possible, consistent with the regulations established from time to time under this Convention. The rules established under this Convention shall apply to the high seas. Each contracting State undertakes to ensure the prosecution of all persons who break the applicable regulations. " As it results from the regulation, the tasks of each state-party to the Convention include establishing the internal flight regime in their airspace. While in the case of cross-border civil commercial flights that are meticulously planned and prepared to comply with the rules of the air in the space of each state over whose territory a crewed aircraft is flown is a normal part of the flight plan, the situation may be difficult in the case of unmanned aerial

vehicles. Well, users of drones using them for flights for recreational or professional purposes, but without transporting passengers (e.g. for filming or delivering goods), must also often face the fact that the drone piloted / controlled by them crosses the state borders during the flight, hence it is already subject to a different legal regime, which also includes air traffic regulations[1]. For many non-large-scale airline operators (such as airlines), this legal "fragmentation" can be highly embarrassing and thus discouraging the use of UAVs for cross-border operations. Hence the significant need to unify air traffic regulations, at least at the regional level.

The most important legal acts of the European Union in the field of unmanned aerial vehicles include, among others [4]:

1. Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/945 (hereinafter "Regulation 2019/945") of 12 March 2019 on unmanned aerial systems and operators of unmanned aerial systems of third countries.
2. Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947 (hereinafter "Regulation 2019/947") of 24 May 2019 on the rules and procedures for the operation of unmanned aerial vehicles.

Both legal acts provide definitions related to unmanned aerial vehicles. Regulation 2019/945 of March 12, 2019 states that "(...) unmanned aerial vehicle means any aircraft operated or intended to be operated without a pilot on board, which may operate autonomously or be piloted remotely." On the other hand, Regulation 2019/947 of May 24, 2019 extends the scope of the concept, taking into account that, apart from the unit itself, the unmanned aerial vehicle should also be understood as the equipment for remote control of the ship.

The new regulations entered into force, obliging Member States to adapt existing internal regulations to the new EU law. The Union itself assumes that by June 2021 national regulations will be compatible with European Union law. It is assumed that the overriding goal of introducing new regulations is, first of all, to ensure the common security of unmanned aerial vehicle operations and to protect the privacy of EU citizens, while allowing free access to the airspace for unmanned aerial vehicles. This is stated in the Preamble to Regulation 2019/947 in point 1: "Unmanned aerial vehicles, regardless of their weight, may be operated within the single European airspace alongside manned aircraft, both airplanes and helicopters".

From the point of view of air traffic and its safety, Art. 3 of Regulation 2019/947, which introduces three categories of UAS operations:

- "open" category, which means the UAS operation category as defined in Art. 4 of the regulation;
- "specific" category, which means the UAS operation category as defined in Art. 5 of the regulation;
- "certified" category, which means the UAS operation category as defined in Art. 6 of the Regulation.

Each of the categories included in the following articles introduces increasingly restrictive regulations regarding the use of drones in the airspace. To classify an operation as "open", it must cumulatively meet the following conditions[5]:

- a) UAV belongs to one of the classes specified in Regulation 2019/945 or was constructed for private use, or meets the conditions specified in Art. 20;
- b) UAV has a maximum take-off mass of less than 25 kg;
- c) the UAV pilot ensures that the unmanned aerial vehicle maintains a safe distance from people and that its flight does not pass over assemblies of people;
- d) the UAV pilot keeps the unit within the visual range of the VLOS at all times (with a few exceptions referred to in the rule);
- e) during the flight, the UAV is kept at a distance of not more than 120 meters from the nearest point of the earth's surface, except when it is flying over an obstacle;
- f) during the flight, the UAV does not carry any hazardous materials, nor does it drop any materials.

If any of the above conditions is not met, then the operation is considered to be "special" and the operator must obtain prior approval from a state authority to perform it. However, an operation can be "certified" if:

- a) the UAV carrying it out falls under the "certified" category in accordance with Regulation 2019/945;
- b) is performed over assemblies of people;
- c) involves the carriage of passengers;
- d) involves the carriage of dangerous goods.

Further provisions of Regulation 2019/947 relate, inter alia, to the competence of pilots of unmanned ships, their minimum age, certification procedures, etc.

On the other hand, Regulation 2019/945 functions as an act regulating the design and production of UAVs intended for operation in accordance with the principles and conditions set out in Regulation 2019/947, as well as placing on the market and thus subjecting to free movement of drones operated under the "open" category. Finally, the Regulation's task is to establish the rules for the use of UAVs by operators from third countries (all this is laid down in Article 1). It can therefore be seen that, unlike Regulation 2019/947, whose task is primarily to create a framework for the safe use of all types of drones on the territory of EU countries, Regulation 2019/945 is intended to ensure that already at the production stage, and then introduced into in the free market, these machines were safe and, where there was a high degree of risk of use, properly certified. Thus, the obligations set out in this Regulation are borne by entities such as producers, distributors or importers.

At the same time, the EU legislator should be appreciated for a fairly rational approach to the issue. Similarly, to Regulation 2019/947, this regulation also categorizes drone operations into "open", "special" and "certified", while imposing stricter certification obligations for those units whose operation is associated with a higher risk.

As the delegated regulations are directly applicable, no additional legal acts by the Member States will be required for their application.

It must be emphasized that with the publication of these regulations by the Commission there is no direct application of them, since EASA, the European Agency for Air Safety and the rest of the state agencies or competent bodies of each of the member states, they must publish the Acceptable Means of Compliance and the Guide Material to make these regulations practical. Each of the regulations includes a period of entry into force, even differentiated by parts of them.

4.1. Regulation 2019/945

This regulation establishes the requirements for the design and manufacture of unmanned aircraft systems (UAS in regulation 2019/947). It also deals with the commercialization requirements of the UAS for an open category in Chapter II, including the systems or accessories that they must have. Chapter III is applicable to UAS for specific

category and certified category, establishing its requirements in terms of design, production and maintenance and use according to the purposes. Chapter IV talks about the operations carried out by operators from third countries that are not from the European Union.

One of the most important parts of Regulation 2019/945 is Annex I, where the UAS classes are established. In response to its maximum take-off mass, the following classes are established:

- C0: MMD <250g;
- C1: MMD <900g;
- C2: MMD <4kg;
- C3: MMD <25kg;
- C4: MMD <25kg without automatic control modes, or model airplanes.

Each of the classes has a series of requirements for its manufacture and obtaining the CE marking, necessary for its commercialization in the EU. It is worth highlighting several novelties or curiosities:

- Height limitation system on the take-off point of the aircraft at 120m or above ground. If the height is selectable by the pilot, the system must have a reading of the height on the ground at all times, so as not to exceed the aforementioned limitation.
- Direct identification system that aircraft should have from class C1. A system that allows and guarantees, in accordance with the regulations, in real time during the entire duration of the flight, the direct periodic dissemination of relevant information from the aircraft using an open and documented transmission protocol, including a unique registration number and data about the operator. A system that will allow drones to be monitored in airspace along with 5G and IoT telecommunications technologies.

There is also information about geoscience or geofencing systems, although they are not as novel and the drones already carry them. Although the current geoscience systems (such as the DJI NFZ) do not use data from aeronautical information systems or aeronautical charts, as it does require that the new regulation must be made.

There is also information about the manuals and maintenance instructions that should have been prepared from UAV class C1.

Although the 2019/947 regulation establishes a transitory period of use for current equipment that does not comply with the previous requirements, in the Article 20 thereof, until 2022.

4.2. Regulation 2019/947

Regulation 2019/947 establishes the normal and regulations for the use of UAS in European airspace, which will come into force on July 1, 2020.

In the annex, OPEN-open, SPECIFIC-specific or CERTIFIED-certified operation categories are established.

For the Open category, the subcategories A1, A2 and A3 are established, depending on the type of operation, its area of flight and the type of aircraft used.

Subcategory A1 is established for drones of less than 250g or classes C0 or C1, avoiding flight over concentrations of people for classes C0 or less than 250g (if it does not meet the requirements of Regulation 2019/945) or about people for the class C1. For this category it will be necessary to know the equipment user manual as well as to have an online training course for class C1 aircraft.

The subcategory A2 establishes for aircraft of class C2, with the possibility of making flights of more than 30m horizontal distance over people (never over them) or up to 5m with the necessary precautions. The responsible drivers must have knowledge of the team's user manual, the online training course (which will be valid for 5 years), a self-study course and passing an exam carried out by the competent authority of each member state.

The subcategory A3 establishes the training conditions of the pilot as those of the subcategory A2 and the flight scenario should not be about people besides saving 150m with respect to populated areas. Aircraft of classes C2, C3, C4 or less than 25kg of maximum take-off mass may be used.

For flights in a specific category, the operator must have an operational authorization, which may be punctual for one or several operations or may have a CAA approval (light UAS

operator certificate) as specified in Annex Part C. For this purpose, the operator must perform a risk assessment subject to the conditions set out in the regulations.

The competent authority will establish standard scenarios, specified in appendix 1, which will result in the operator not having to have an operational authorization but with a declaration, it is understood that under the declaration of responsible regime.

The regulation in article 15 establishes the operational conditions applicable to the geographical areas of the UAS for reasons of security, protection, privacy or environment. The member states are allowed the ability to prohibit, restrict or impose the specific conditions for each specific area, as established today with areas of controlled airspace, prohibited, restricted, dangerous or wildlife protection zones.

Authorizations granted to UAS operators, certificates of competence of remote pilots and statements submitted by UAS operators or equivalent documentation, issued on the basis of national law, will remain valid until July 1, 2021. Member States shall, by 1 July 2021, convert their current remote pilot competence certificates and their authorizations or declarations of UAS operators, or equivalent documentation, including those issued up to that date, in accordance with this regulation.

In transitory dispositions the use of UAS in open category is also established, different to those contemplated in regulation 2019/945 until 2022, establishing its classification according to weight.

The new rules are an important step for the industry. The legislation defines the requirements for drone capabilities for achieving maximal safety. An example of such a condition is ensuring an individual identification of every drone that will enable national authorities to better react to certain situations when necessary.

Moreover, the EU-wide rules provide unprecedented flexibility to both recreational and professional drone users. According to the laws, operators will be required to register their drones in the Member State where they reside or conduct business. Once pilots receive a permit from a European Union state, they will have the freedom to fly their drones across the whole EU.

Further EASA actions should be focused on the provision of materials to assist the involved parties in complying with the adopted legislation.

Summary

The use of a drone to control compliance with environmental protection regulations is effective and efficient. Firstly, the anti-smog drone allows you to operate not only within a specific property but also often in a district. This makes the control effective. Secondly - drone control does not require prior notification of the control. Thirdly, if the drone detects the wrong fuel, the sample can be taken and sent to the laboratory.

It is also worth remembering that from December 31, 2020, the same regulations for drones resulting directly from EU regulations apply throughout the European Union. According to the new regulations, every operator, amateur or professional must have a registration number. The exception is only for UAVs weighing up to 250 grams without a camera, loudspeaker or other sensors. And these are not used for anti-smog activities. So every operator has to register, and before that happens, undergo online training and pass a test.

The term "anti-smog control" in Poland in 2021 is used in relation to activities consisting in checking the quality of fuels burned in heating boilers in terms of compliance with the provisions of the Waste Act, the Environmental Protection Law and the Penal Code.

Technological development, including the popularization and availability of unmanned aerial vehicles, resulted in the use of this type of equipment to perform measurements. However, the samples taken by the ship do not constitute sufficient evidence that the wrong type of fuel has been used and may be challenged in court. In order to collect irrefutable evidence, it is still necessary to collect the ash generated during the incineration during the on-site inspection (also pursuant to Art. 379 of the Wednesday Act). Performing pre-control with the use of an unmanned aerial vehicle, however, has a spectacular value and is one of the preliminary activities consisting in checking the risk of using raw materials that are illegal and for their intended use. The approach of local communities towards breaking the law and the fear of proper control make the use of an unmanned aerial vehicle during an inspection an effective tool for disciplining citizens to comply with the law, which contributes to the improvement of air quality in Poland.

References

- [1] N. Tuśnio, A. Nowak, J. Tuśnio, P. Wolny, Bezzałogowe statki powietrzne w działaniach Państwowej Straży Pożarnej – propozycja dedykowana Państwowej Straży Pożarnej The Unmanned Aerial Vehicles in Fire Fighting Operations – the Proposal Dedicated for State Fire Service Zeszyty SGSP 2016, Vol. 58 (tome 1)/2/2016.
- [2] K. Kostur, M. Żmigrodzka, T. Balcerzak, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles In Fire Protection [Bezzałogowe Statki Powietrzne w Ochronie Przeciwpowozarowej, www.eumed.net , (Access: 21.02.2022).
- [3] A. Fellner, A. Mańka, R. Fellner, Drony–bezpieczeństwo i zagrożenia Komunikacja Publiczna, 2016, pp. 35f.
- [4] Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/945 of 12 March 2019 on unmanned aircraft systems and on third-country operators of unmanned aircraft systems, Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947 of 24 May 2019 on the rules and procedures for the operation of unmanned aircraft.
- [5] Regardless of the weight of the drone, it is prohibited to fly over enclosed areas, nuclear facilities, military units and training grounds, as well as such facilities as power plants, heating plants, aqueducts, sewage plants, special production facilities, etc. (Art. 5 para. 2(1)(a) and (b), (2)(a) and (b), (3)(a) and (b) of the Act of 22 August 1997 on the protection of persons and property (i.e. Journal Of Laws of 2018, item 2142 and 2245).
- [6] S. Babiarz, U-space: From Blueprint to Reality, <https://www.aerosociety.com/media/7267/u-space-blueprint-to-reality.pdf>, (Access: 21.02.2022).
- [7] Anna Konert, Piotr Kasprzyk, Drones Are Flying outside of Segregated Airspace in Poland, Journal of Intelligent & Robotic Systems 2020, https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10846-019-01145-4?wt_mc=Internal.Event.1.SEM.ArticleAuthorOnlineFirst&utm_source=ArticleAuthorOnlineFirst&utm_medium=email&utm_content=AA_en_06082018&ArticleAuthorOnlineFirst_20200118 , (Access: 21.02.2022).
- [8] Environmental Protection Law of 21 April 2001 (Journal of Laws of 2021, item 1973).
- [9] Regulation of the Minister of Infrastructure and Construction of 8 August 2016 amending the Regulation on exclusion of the application of certain provisions of the Aviation Law Act to certain types of aircraft and determining the conditions and requirements for the use of these vessels (Journal of Laws of 2016, item 1317).
- [10] Convention on International Civil Aviation, Signed in Chicago on 7 December 1944 - Chicago Convention (Journal of Laws of 1959, No. 35, Item 212, As Amended).